

Figure 1. Search Strategies		
Database	Term Search	Citation Searches
PubMed	"Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool"[tw] OR "ToxRTool"[tw] OR "ToxR-Tool"[tw]	1Schneider et al. Search 19477248 Segal et al. Search 25777839 Koch et al. Search 25208336
Embase	('Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool' OR 'ToxRTool' OR 'ToxR-Tool');ti,ab,kw	Not applicable. Embase does not provide independent citation-based searching. It just provides links to citing papers in Scopus.
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY("Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool" OR "ToxRTool" OR "ToxR-Tool")	2TITLE("ToxRTool", a new tool to assess the reliability of toxicological data") TITLE("Evaluation of the ToxRTool's ability to rate the reliability of toxicological data for human health hazard assessments") TITLE("Adaptation of the ToxRTool to Assess the Reliability of Toxicology Studies Conducted with Genetically Modified Crops and Implications for Future Safety Testing")
Web of Science	TS=("Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool" OR "ToxRTool" OR "ToxR-Tool")	3TI=("ToxRTool, a new tool to assess the reliability of toxicological data") TI=("Evaluation of the ToxRTool's ability to rate the reliability of toxicological data for human health hazard assessments") TI=("Adaptation of the ToxRTool to Assess the Reliability of Toxicology Studies Conducted with Genetically Modified Crops and Implications for Future Safety Testing")
Google Scholar	"Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool" OR "ToxRTool" OR "ToxR-Tool"	4"ToxRTool, a new tool to assess the reliability of toxicological data" "Evaluation of the ToxRTool's ability to rate the reliability of toxicological data for human health hazard assessments" "Adaptation of the ToxRTool to Assess the Reliability of Toxicology Studies Conducted with Genetically Modified Crops and Implications for Future Safety Testing"

Figure 1. Search Strategies. This table summarises the search strategies applied to each database listed in the row. The following numbers clarify some of the nuances associated with each database: 1) Citation Searches - By PMID - "See all 'Cited by' articles", 2) Citation Searches - "View all citing documents", 3) Citation Searches - "Citations", and 4) "Citation Searches - "Cited by."